

Medicinal Plants in Female Reproductive Health: A Systematic Review of Experimental Animal Evidence on Ovarian Function and Fertility

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Background and issue addressed

Female reproductive health relies on the co-ordinated regulation of ovarian and endocrine functions, including folliculogenesis, steroidogenesis, ovulation and endocrine signaling (1). Disruptions in these physiological processes cause wide range of reproductive disorders, including ovulatory dysfunction, infertility and endocrine disorders, contributing to the pathogenesis of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) (2). These conditions represent a significant health burden for reproductive-age females and are associated with substantial reproductive, psychological and socioeconomic consequences (3).

Medicinal plants are being part of traditional systems of medicine, such as Ayurveda, to support female reproductive health. In recent years, increasing scientific interest has focused on plant-derived interventions, including whole medicinal plants, plant extracts, plant fractions and phytoconstituents, as potential modulators of ovarian function (4,5). Unlike conventional single-target therapies, plant-derived interventions contain multiple bioactive constituents that may exert their biological effects through the simultaneous modulation of multiple molecular targets and signaling pathways (6,7). Consequently, their therapeutic effects are often attributed to the combined and potentially synergistic actions of multiple constituents rather than a single isolated compound. This multi-component, multi-target mode of action may be particularly relevant to female reproductive disorders, which involve complex interactions among hormonal, metabolic, inflammatory and ovarian regulatory pathways (8,9). For this review, the term "plant-derived interventions" refers to whole medicinal plants, plant extracts, plant fractions and plant-based polyherbal formulations.

A growing number of experimental rodent animal studies have evaluated the effects of plant-derived interventions on ovarian morphology, folliculogenesis, ovulation, reproductive hormone levels, estrous cyclicity and fertility-related outcomes. These studies have investigated a wide variety of plant species, extraction methods, doses, treatment durations, and disease models, generating substantial evidence regarding their potential role in female reproductive health. Thus, the experimental rodent animal studies can serve as scientific evidences supporting the beneficial effects of plant-derived interventions for female reproductive health.

Rationale for the review

However, no comprehensive systematic review has been reported and critically evaluated despite the increasing volume of experimental rodent animal evidence. Consequently, it remains unclear which plant-derived interventions demonstrate the most consistent beneficial effects on ovarian function and fertility-related outcomes, whether these effects are reproducible across different animal models and reproductive disorders, and which interventions possess the strongest evidence to support future translational research. Furthermore, methodological heterogeneity in animal models, intervention characteristics, and outcome assessment affect the reliability and interpretation of reported findings. This lack of synthesis limits evidence-based prioritization of promising interventions and the identification of key research gaps.

Reporting evidence from experimental animal studies is an important step in the translational research pathway. Animal studies provide essential information regarding biological efficacy, mechanisms of action, dose-response relationships and safety of test interventions before their clinical evaluation in humans. A systematic evaluation of the available evidence may help to identify promising plant-derived interventions for future investigations, highlight gaps in current knowledge and guide future research in the field.

Therefore, this systematic review aims to systematically identify and report evidence from experimental animal studies investigating the effects of plant-derived interventions on ovarian function and female reproductive outcomes.

Specifically, this review will:

- Identify plant-derived interventions investigated in experimental rodent animal models of female reproductive physiology and reproductive disorders.
- Evaluate the effects plant-derived interventions on ovarian function, including folliculogenesis, ovulation, steroidogenesis, and ovarian morphology.
- Summarize proposed biological mechanisms and identify evidence gaps to inform future translational and clinical research.

1. Review Title and Basic Details

1.1. Review Title

Medicinal Plants in Female Reproductive Health: A Systematic Review of Experimental Animal Evidence on Ovarian Function and Fertility

1.2. Condition or domain being studied

Female reproductive function and ovarian physiology, hyperandrogenism, folliculogenesis, ovulation and fertility outcomes.

1.3. Review objectives:

1.3.1. Primary objective

To systematically identify and report available evidence on the effects of plant-derived interventions on ovarian function and female reproductive outcomes in experimental animal models.

1.3.2. Secondary objectives

1. To identify and categorize the medicinal plants, plant extracts, fractions and polyherbal formulations investigated in experimental animal models for their effects on female reproductive physiology and ovarian function.
2. To evaluate the reported effects of plant-derived interventions on reproductive outcomes such as follicular development, ovarian morphology, steroidogenesis, ovulation, hormonal regulation and fertility-related parameters.
3. To examine the biological mechanisms through which plant-derived interventions influence ovarian function, including oxidative stress, inflammation, endocrine signaling, histopathological alterations, and other molecular pathways.

1.4. Keywords

Female reproductive health, Folliculogenesis, Medicinal plants, Ovarian function, Plant extracts

2. Eligibility criteria

2.1. Population

2.1.1. Inclusion:

Experimental rodent animal models relevant to female reproductive physiology or reproductive disorders.

2.1.2. Exclusion:

- Clinical studies
- *In-vitro* or *ex-vivo* studies
- Studies focusing exclusively on male reproductive biology.

2.2. Intervention(s) or exposure(s)

2.2.1 Inclusion:

Studies investigating medicinal plants, plant extracts, plant fractions and polyherbal formulations.

2.2.2 Exclusion

Studies investigating isolated phytoconstituents, synthetic drugs or non-plant-derived compounds involving marine and microbial products.

2.3 Comparator(s) or control(s)

2.3.1 Inclusion:

Studies including at least one comparator group, such as:

- Untreated control
- Vehicle control
- Disease control
- Positive control or standard treatment
- Baseline comparison

2.3.2 Exclusion:

Studies without a comparator group

2.4 Outcomes

2.4.1 Inclusion:

Studies reporting outcomes related to female reproductive physiology or ovarian function, including:

- Folliculogenesis or follicular development
- Ovarian morphology or follicle count
- Ovulation
- Steroidogenesis
- Reproductive hormone levels (e.g., estrogen, progesterone, LH, FSH, testosterone)
- Estrous cycle regulation
- Fertility-related outcomes (e.g., mating success, conception rate, pregnancy rate, litter size, offspring number)

- Ovarian oxidative stress markers
- Inflammatory markers related to ovarian function
- Endocrine signaling pathways
- Histopathological changes in ovarian tissue
- Molecular mechanisms associated with ovarian function and fertility

2.4.2 Exclusion:

- Studies reporting only antioxidant, metabolic or biochemical effects without reproductive outcomes.

2.5 Study design

2.5.1 Inclusion criteria

- Experimental rodent animal studies

2.5.2 Exclusion criteria

- Review articles
- Systematic reviews and meta-analyses
- Editorials and commentaries
- Conference abstracts without full data
- *In-vitro* mechanistic studies

3. Timeline

Start date: 1st June 2026; End date: 31st May 2027

4. Data Collection Process

4.1. Searching and Screening

The search will utilize the following databases:

- PubMed
- Scopus
- Web of Science

4.2. Data Extraction from Included Studies

A standardized data extraction form will be developed and used to systematically collect relevant information from all included studies.

The following data will be extracted:

Study Identification

- Authors
- Year of publication
- Country of study

Study Characteristics

- Disease model (PCOS, ovarian toxicity, reproductive aging, etc.)
- Animal species and strain
- Animal age and weight (if reported)
- Plant name and family
- Plant part used
- Type of intervention (whole plant, extract, or fraction)
- Extraction method/solvent
- Extract standardization (if reported)
- Route of administration
- Dose(s)
- Duration of treatment
- Comparator/control type
- Funding source
- Conflicts of interest

Outcome Measures

- Folliculogenesis and follicular development
- Ovulation
- Steroidogenesis
- Reproductive hormone levels (estrogen, progesterone, LH, FSH, testosterone)
- Fertility-related outcomes (mating success, conception rate, pregnancy rate, litter size, offspring number)
- Ovarian morphology and follicle count
- Estrous cycle regulation
- Oxidative stress markers
- Inflammatory markers
- Endocrine signaling pathways
- Histopathological changes in ovarian tissue
- Molecular mechanisms associated with ovarian function and fertility

Key Findings

- Direction of effect (increase/decrease/no effect)
- Statistical significance (if reported)

Mechanistic Insights

- Oxidative stress markers
- Hormonal regulation pathways
- Cellular or molecular observations

4.3. Risk of Bias / Quality Assessment

To critically appraise the methodological quality and assess the risk of bias of the included experimental animal studies, the SYRCLE Risk of Bias tool will be used (10).

4.4. Reporting Bias Assessment

If sufficient studies are available for quantitative synthesis:

- Funnel plots will be generated
- Egger's regression test will be performed to assess publication bias (11).

4.5. Certainty of Evidence

The certainty of evidence will be assessed using an adapted GRADE (Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation) approach for preclinical animal studies (12). The overall certainty of evidence will be evaluated across the following domains:

- Risk of bias
- Inconsistency of results
- Indirectness of evidence
- Imprecision of effect estimates
- Publication bias

5. Outcomes to be Analysed

- Folliculogenesis and follicular development
- Ovulation
- Steroidogenesis
- Reproductive hormone levels (estrogen, progesterone, LH, FSH, testosterone)

- Fertility-related outcomes (mating success, conception rate, pregnancy rate, litter size, offspring number)
- Ovarian morphology and follicle count
- Estrous cycle regulation
- Oxidative stress markers
- Inflammatory markers
- Endocrine signaling pathways
- Histopathological changes in ovarian tissue
- Molecular mechanisms associated with ovarian function and fertility

6. Planned Data Synthesis

6.1. Strategy for Data Synthesis

6.1.1. Descriptive (Narrative) Synthesis

A narrative synthesis will be conducted to summarize findings across included studies.

Studies will first be grouped according to medicinal plant species and intervention type (whole plant, extract, or fraction), followed by synthesis according to outcomes including folliculogenesis, ovarian morphology, ovulation, steroidogenesis, hormonal regulation and fertility-related outcomes.

Presentation of Results

Data will be summarized in tables including:

- Plant name
- Type of extract/fraction
- Model used
- Outcomes measured
- Key findings

6.1.2. Quantitative Synthesis (Meta-Analysis)

If sufficient homogeneity exists across studies:

- Meta-analysis will be conducted using random-effects models (13)

Heterogeneity will be assessed using:

- I^2 statistic

Meta-analysis will only be performed when studies are sufficiently comparable in terms of:

- intervention

- model
- outcome measures

Otherwise, findings will be synthesized narratively.

6.1.3. Subgroup Analysis (If Feasible)

Subgroup analyses may be conducted based on:

- Type of intervention (extract vs fraction)
- Type of outcome (hormonal vs fertility vs morphological)
- Species
- Disease model
- Plant species
- Extract type
- Dose(s)
- Treatment duration
- Route of administration

6.1.4. Sensitivity Analysis

Sensitivity analyses will be conducted where applicable by:

- Exclusion of studies judged to be at high risk of bias according to the SYRCLE Risk of Bias tool
- Exclusion of studies with inadequate or incomplete reporting of methodological or outcome data

6.1.5. Assessment of Publication Bias

Funnel plots and Egger's regression test will be performed only when at least 10 studies contribute to a meta-analysis.

6.1.6. Reporting

The systematic review will be reported in accordance with: PRISMA 2020 (14)

Results will be presented using:

- Summary tables
- Narrative synthesis
- Forest plots (if meta-analysis is conducted)

7. References

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